

NEW METHODS OF TEACHING RUSSIAN TO STUDENTS IN HIGHER
EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS.

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Xasanova Parizod Rafiq qizi

Teacher, National University of Uzbekistan

Abstract: The idea of humanization and humanitarianization of education is becoming a priority in our society. The need to integrate technical and humanitarian knowledge, the ways of such a synthesis are actively discussed by teachers of higher education. The university should produce a specialist with a high cultural level, which was often emphasized by well-known methodologists. The following article is devoted to the innovative methods of teaching Russian in higher education institutions.

Keywords: method, methodology, digital technology, perception, speech, rhythm, speed, melody.

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Our century is the "information age", "the age of new technologies", "the age of education". The development of education remains one of the priority state directions, since it is high-quality education that is the basis of the innovative development of any country. The modernization of the education system, the ongoing changes in the system of higher education are due to the movement towards an innovative personality-developing paradigm of education, the need to use the intellectual and creative potential of a person for creative activity in all spheres of life. The change in the content of education consists in a gradual transition from educational and subject-based activities based on the assimilation of the fundamentals of sciences, knowledge, skills and habits, to a focus on the mastery of each student (taking into account the characteristics of his development) in aggregate universal skills.

The construction of the content of education, taking into account modern trends in the development of scientific knowledge, leads to the need, as the main units of assimilation, to single out not only concepts, but also those cognitive means that help the student independently acquire knowledge through mastery of intellectual actions that develop thought processes.

The methodology of teaching the Russian language (native) language at the university is an independent pedagogical science. Deep knowledge of methodology is a necessary condition for teacher training. A modern teacher should be well educated: be proficient in the norms of the literary language, have a good knowledge of the content and system of work on the Russian language at the university, the educational possibilities of the subject "Russian language",

assimilate the theoretical foundations and principles of teaching the Russian language at the university, know the basic methodological methods of educational work and be able to apply them, know the leading directions in the development of methodology as a science, research of recent decades and problems awaiting their solution.

The modern stage of the development of civilization requires specialists with broad humanitarian thinking, able to build competently professional activities according to the laws of harmonious development. But we are talking not only about the fact that an engineering and technical worker must have a sufficient level of intellectual training in order to be able to ensure the effectiveness of his work. No less important is the fact that it is humanitarian knowledge that gives such priorities as responsibility for universally significant values, worldview self-determination, general cultural competence, personal self-actualization.

Teaching the Russian language should involve all aspects of students' speech activity. Speech activity is an active, purposeful process of transmitting or receiving a message mediated by the language system and determined by the situation of communication. This is a system of skills aimed at solving various communication problems. We are talking about communicative tasks, combined on the basis of the following features: a) the form of speech - oral or written; b) perception or generation of speech. Traditionally, speech activity is divided into 4 types: listening (oral, perception), speaking (oral, production), reading (writing, perception), writing (writing, production).

In modern methodology, there is a desire to bring the conditions of the educational process closer to the conditions of free communication. In this regard, much attention is paid to the development of skills in all four types of speech activity. There is such a term as interconnected learning, which involves the parallel and balanced formation of four types of speech activity based on common language material within their sequential-temporal relationship. Listening, speaking, reading and writing is both a goal and a means of learning. Work on these types of speech activity is carried out in a certain sequence within the framework of a practical lesson or a cycle of classes, in which general language material is mandatory. In the communicative-activity approach, the most common methodological unit of the organization of language material is the topic, which is understood as a fragment of reality reflected in our minds and fixed with the help of language. Within the framework of the topic, certain lexical and grammatical material should be presented in all types of speech activity, which ensures better assimilation of linguistic material through the activation of auditory, visual and motor analyzers. The formation of communicatively significant skills and abilities

is carried out with the help of a series of specially designed exercises, which present the studied lexical and grammatical material on a particular topic.

Practical classes contain a variety of exercises for practicing and consolidating language skills. Imitative, substitution, transformational, reproductive and speech tasks are aimed at the formation of the student's language, speech and communicative competencies in their professional field.

The traditional method of teaching the Russian language in schools and universities paid great attention to literate writing. However, this violated one of the basic laws of psycholinguistics, which is that all types of speech activity in the learning process should be formed in unity and in interconnection. In the 21st century, the anthropocentric orientation of linguistics made it possible to turn to the immediate goal of teaching the language as a means of communication.

The term "listening" is opposed to the term "listening". "Listening" - acoustic perception of the scale. The concept of listening, in turn, includes the perception and understanding of sounding speech. Listening is a complex aspect of speech activity. Many modern ypoel graduates practically do not possess this skill. Mastering listening makes it possible to realize educational, educational and developmental goals. Through listening, we nurture a culture of communication. In addition, human auditory memory develops.

Listening is a powerful tool for teaching a language, which makes it possible to master the sound side of the language being studied, its phonemic composition and intonation: rhythm, stress, melody. Listening as an action that is part of oral communicative activity is actively used in any oral communication subject to production, social or personal needs. Listening, as feedback from each speaker during speaking, allows you to exercise self-control over speech and know how correctly speech intentions are realized in sound form.

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